

Galactocerebroside and other secondary metabolites of sea mouse

Chloeia parva^{1-4,†}

Amarendra Patra*, Kalyan Kumar Mandal and Anadi Majumdar

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, University of Calcutta, 92, A. P. C. Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : amarendra@satyam.net.in Fax : 91-33-23519755

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Novel galactocerebrosides derived from 2-amino-4-alkene-1,3-diol along with fatty acid methyl esters (FAME), cholesterol, ceramides, 1-*O*-acylglycerols and 1-*O*-alkylglycerols have been isolated from a sea mouse *Chloeia parva*. The structure of galactocerebrosides is established from one-dimensional [¹H, homodecoupling and ¹³C (NDC and DEPT-135)] NMR spectral studies of the metabolite and its acetate as well as two-dimensional (COSY-90, X-H correlation optimized for ¹J_{C-H}) NMR spectral studies of the latter. The remaining components isolated have been characterized from chemical studies and detailed NMR spectral analyses of parent materials and products derived thereof. The lengths of the alkyl and acyl chains in galactocerebrosides, FAME, ceramides, 1-*O*-acylglycerols and 1-*O*-alkylglycerols are established by gas chromatographic analysis of appropriate derivatives.

Past three decades have witnessed a tremendous surge of interests in marine natural product research throughout the globe⁵. As a part of our search for bioactive components from marine sources a sea mouse, *Chloeia parva* was collected from the Eastern coast of the Bay of Bengal, adjoining West Bengal. This paper deals with the results of the chemical investigations including the structural elaboration of interesting and novel marine metabolites, galactocerebrosides. Cerebrosides are important membrane components in both plant and animal cells, and they appear to participate in cell regulatory functions and trans-membrane signaling. Such galactocerebrosides have earlier been reported⁴ from star fish (*Pentacaster regulas*⁶), sponge (*Chondropsis* sp.^{7,8}, *Halichondria japonica*⁹, *Halichondria panicea*¹⁰, *Agelas longissima*¹¹⁻¹³, *Agelas clathrodes*¹⁴, *Agelas conifera*¹⁵, *Agelas dispar*¹⁶, *Agelas* sp.¹⁷, *Axinella* sp.¹⁸, *Plakortis simplex*¹⁹ and *Agelas mauritanus*^{20,21}), sea star (*Stellaster equestris*²² and *Astropecten latespinosis*²³), annelid (*Marphysa sanguinea*²⁴) and red algae (*Corallina pilulifera*²⁵) and continue to attract the attention of investigators because of their structural complexity and wide range of biological activities, e.g., coronary vasodilators, antiherpertensive and histidine carboxylase inhibitors^{7,8}, cytotoxic^{17,23}, immunosuppressive properties¹⁹, antitumour and immunostimulatory^{20,21}, active ingredients for the treatment of AIDS and HIV-related diseases²⁶ and inhibited the entry

of HIV-I in neural cell line²⁷.

Results and discussion

The sea mouse *Chloeia parva* was crushed mechanically and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ followed by CH₂Cl₂-MeOH (1 : 1). The CH₂Cl₂ and CH₂Cl₂-MeOH (1 : 1) extracts were then subjected separately to column chromatography with silica gel and the residues from different fractions obtained therefrom were then applied to preparative tlc. The CH₂Cl₂-MeOH (1 : 1) extract of the organism afforded mainly galactocerebrosides (1), *R_f* ~0.3 in CHCl₃-MeOH (90 : 10), [α]_D²⁵ -1.4° (*c* 0.96, MeOH) in about 0.00035% yield (wet weight) while the CH₂Cl₂ extract yielded 1-*O*-acylglycerol (2) together with other ubiquitous compounds viz., ceramide (3), 1-*O*-alkylglycerol (4), cholesterol (5) and fatty acid methyl ester (FAME, 6). These compounds have been characterized from chemical studies, detailed NMR spectral analyses of both parent materials and derived products as well as from gas chromatographic analyses of appropriate derivatives for establishing alkyl chain lengths.

Galactocerebroside :

The UV spectrum of the component 1 in aldehyde free ethanol showed no characteristics absorption for conjugated chromophore. The IR spectrum of the material displayed absorption bands for the presence of -OH and -NHCO- functions and methylene units. The detailed 1D (¹H-, ¹³C-, homodecoupling) and 2D (COSY and XHCORR)

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji.

NMR experiments of the metabolite and its pentaacetate were in consonance with formulations **1** and **7** respectively. The ^1H spectrum of the component **1** in $\text{CDCl}_3\text{-CD}_3\text{OD}$ displayed a signal at δ 5.59 (1H, d, J 6.5 Hz, very slowly exchangeable by D_2O) for an amide proton (-CONH-) that was coupled to a multiplet signal at δ 3.93 (1H). The spectrum also showed few signals in the 3.3–4.2 ppm region and most of them were for the protons on oxygenated carbons as in a sugar moiety of a glycoside. Besides, the ^1H spectrum contained the signals at δ 5.61 (1H, dt, J 15.2 and 5.7 Hz) and 5.39 (1H, dd, J 15.2 and 7.3 Hz) likely for the *trans* oriented olefinic protons, 4.15 (1H, d, J 6.5 Hz) for glycosidic proton, 2.02 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz) for the ketomethylene protons, 1.88 (2H, m) for the allylic protons, 1.25 (huge, br.s) for a number of methylene protons of the long chain alkyl moiety and 0.74 (6H, t, J 6.6 Hz) for the terminal methyls.

The component **1** in its ^{13}C spectrum showed oxymethylene carbon resonances at δ 103.6, 73.4, 72.2, 71.2, 69.0 along with the oxymethyl carbon resonance at δ 61.6 consistent with the presence of a pyranoside unit where δ 103.6 signal was due to the anomeric carbon. Again, the spectrum also displayed another oxymethylene carbon resonance at δ 74.8, carbon signals for the 1,2-disubstituted olefinic system at δ 134.1 and 128.9, and a carbon resonance at δ 68.7 for the oxymethyl (C-1) carbon in the sphingosine basic unit. The spectrum also had carbon resonances at δ 174.3 for the amide carbonyl as well as methine carbon resonance at δ 53.4 for CH-NH function and ketomethylene (-COCH₂-) carbon resonance at δ 36.4. Assignments of carbon resonances were made by using substituent chemical shift parameters applicable to olefinic and alkyl system^{28–30}. The signals for the terminal methyl carbon and inner methylene carbons of the long aliphatic chain at δ 13.6 and 29.5 respectively were also observed in the ^{13}C spectrum of **1**.

Treatment of the component **1** with Ac_2O -pyridine yielded a pentaacetate **7**, R_f 0.5 in CHCl_3 . The IR spectrum of the product showed new absorption bands at 1750 and 1240 cm^{-1} (for acetate function) along with reduction in intensity of the broad band at 3400–3300 cm^{-1} confirmed the changeover to the acetate **7**. The formation of the pentaacetate upon acetylation was indicated by the generation of five acetate methyl signals at δ 2.16, 2.07, 2.04, 2.03 and 2.00 (3H each, s) in the ^1H spectrum of the acetate **7**. Four of the proton signals that appeared at δ 3.3–4.2 region of the ^1H spectrum of the compound **1** resonated at a downfield position by about 1 ppm while two other by about 0.5 ppm on acetylation and eventually appeared at δ 5.39 (1H, dd, J 3.9 and 3.5 Hz), 5.23 (1H, dd J 7.8 and 2.5 Hz),

1 R = H

7 R = COCH₃

2 R = H

2A R = Ac

2B

3

4 R = H

4A R = Ac

5

6

6A

5.15 (1H, dd, *J* 10.7 and 7.8 Hz), 5.00 (1H, dd, *J* 10.5 and 3.3 Hz), 4.13 (1H, dd, *J* 11.3 and 6.5 Hz) and 4.10 (1H, dd, *J* 11.3 and 6.9 Hz) in the ¹H NMR spectrum of the acetate. The conjoint display of an oxymethylene proton resonance at δ 4.44 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz) in the ¹H spectrum pictured out the presence of *O*-β-D-galactosyl unit as a part of the molecule. The ¹H spectrum of **7** also showed signals for *trans* oriented olefinic protons at δ 5.78 (1H, dt, *J* 14.9 and 6.6 Hz) and 5.37 (1H, dd, *J* 15.1 and 7.4 Hz), a ketomethylene proton at δ 2.19 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), an allylic methylene protons at δ 2.04 (m), a number of methylene protons of the linear alkyl chain at δ 1.25 (huge, br.s) and protons of terminal methyls at δ 0.88 (6H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz) in addition to a signal at δ 5.75 (1H, d, *J* 7.4 Hz, slowly exchangeable by D₂O) for an amide proton. The ¹H spectrum also displayed resonances for a pair of non-equivalent geminally related oxymethyl protons at δ 3.95 (1H, dd, *J* 10.2 and 3.6 Hz) and 3.58 (1H, dd, *J* 10.2 and 4.0 Hz) and two other multiplets at δ 4.30 (1H) and 1.59 (2H).

The proton network in **7** was established by homodecoupling and ¹H-¹H COSY experiments. Further, two-dimensional ¹³C-¹H correlation experiment on the acetate **7** optimized for one-bond C-H coupling allowed identification of the corresponding protonated carbon resonances correlating with the signal/s of the proton/s attached with that carbon. The results are summarised in Table 1.

Homodecoupling as well as COSY-90 experiments established that a doublet signal at δ 4.44 (1H, *J* 7.8 Hz) was coupled with a double-doublet signal at δ 5.15 (1H, *J* 10.7 and 7.8 Hz) which in turn was coupled with a double-doublet signal at δ 5.00 (1H, *J* 10.5 and 3.3 Hz). The latter signal was again coupled to a signal at δ 5.39 (1H, dd, *J* 3.9 and 3.5 Hz). The double-doublet signal at δ 5.39 (1H) was further coupled with a multiplet signal at δ 3.90 (1H) and the latter was related to each of the mutually coupled geminally coupled proton signals at δ 4.13 (1H, dd, *J* 11.3 and 6.5 Hz) and 4.10 (1H, dd, *J* 11.3 and 6.9 Hz). The afore-said observations were in conformity with the presence of an *O*-β-galactopyranoside moiety in the acetate **7** as well as in the parent compound **1**. It has further been noted that a signal at δ 4.30 (1H, m) was coupled to an amide proton signal resonating at δ 5.75 (1H, d, *J* 7.4 Hz), a pair of geminal oxymethyl proton signals at δ 3.95 (1H, dd, *J* 10.2 and 3.6 Hz) and 3.58 (1H, dd, *J* 10.2 and 4.0 Hz) and an acetoxymethylene proton signal at δ 5.23 (1H, dd, *J* 7.8 and 2.5 Hz). The latter signal had coupling interaction with olefinic proton signal at δ 5.37 (1H, dd, *J* 15.1 and 7.4 Hz) that in turn was coupled with a *trans* oriented olefinic proton resonating at δ 5.78 (1H, dt, *J* 14.9 and 6.6 Hz). The

latter signal was further coupled to allylic methylene protons resonating at δ 2.04 (m). Consequently, a basic sphingosine moiety of a ceramide system viz., -OCH₂-CH(NHCOR)CH(OAc)CH=CHCH₂- was present in **7**. Again, the signal at δ 2.19 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz) coupled to a signal at δ 1.59 (2H, m) indicating the presence of a unit like -COCH₂CH₂- in the acetate **7**. The formation of the pentaacetate **7** was also confirmed from the ¹³C NMR spectrum of **1**. In the ¹³C spectrum there were additional methyl signals at δ 21.0 (1C), 20.7 (1C), 20.5 (2C) and 20.4 (1C) and carbonyl signals at δ 172.7, 170.2, 170.1, 169.9, 169.8 and 169.4 accountable for five acetate functions along with an amide carbonyl group. Other carbon signals of the acetate **7** appeared more or less at the similar positions to that of the parent compound **1**.

The composition of the acyl part and also sphingosine basic unit were ascertained by GC analysis of suitable FAME and Alc-OTMS derivatives prepared from it. Reaction involved methanolysis of galactocerebroside (**1**) by refluxing with dry methanol and concentrated H₂SO₄. Subsequent work-up afforded FAME which on GC analysis over 10% DEGS column afforded the composition of the FAME and thus also of the acyl part in cerebroside **1**. The acyl part was composed mainly from the fatty acids 14 : 0 (4.4%), 16 : 0 (28.0), 18 : 0 (16.8), 16 : 1ω9 (9.2), 18 : 1ω9 (13.6), 18 : 2ω6 (2.0), 18 : 3ω3 (6.3) and 22 : 2ω6 (5.3). For the determination of carbon chain length of the basic sphingosine unit the acidic aqueous extract left after removal of FAME by solvent extraction was stirred with a bit of NaNO₂ for half an hour and then refluxed with NaIO₄ in nitrogen atmosphere. Usual work-up yielded a fatty aldehyde that on reduction with KBH₄ followed by trimethylsilylation with trimethylchlorosilane afforded trimethylsilylated alcohol (Alc-OTMS). GLC analysis of Alc-OTMS over 3% SP 2100 column indicated the presence of C₁₆ Alc-OTMS as almost exclusive constituent. Further computation led to the conclusion that a C₁₈ basic sphingosine unit was present in the novel cerebroside **1** which was incidentally a mixture of at least eight major compounds.

Ceramide, 1-O-acylglycerol and 1-O-alkylglycerol :

Further resolution of the residue from CHCl₃-MeOH (95 : 5) eluates of the silica chromatogram of CH₂Cl₂ extract of the organism *Chloëia parva* by preparative tlc afforded a ceramide fraction which was identified as *N*-acyl-erythro-2-amino-4*E*, 8*E*-octadecadiene-1,3-diol (**3**). Levorotation of the ceramide fraction indicates that it belongs to the D-(2*S*,3*R*)-erythro series^{31,32}. The residues from late CHCl₃-MeOH (95 : 5) and earlier CHCl₃-MeOH (90 : 10) eluates of the above chromatogram of CH₂Cl₂ extract were

Table 1. ^{13}C - ^1H , homodecoupling and ^1H - ^1H correlation studies of the pentaacetate 7[§]

^{13}C Signal position (δ) and multiplicity	^{13}C Signal assignment	Proton resonance (δ)		
		showing $^1J_{\text{C-H}}$ correlation	assignments	in homodecoupling and COSY correlation
<i>Methyl</i>				
14 0	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$	0 88, t (6 9)	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$	1 25
20 4	$-\text{OCOCH}_3$	2 06, s	$-\text{OCOCH}_3$	
20 5	$2 \times -\text{OCOCH}_3$	2 03, s, 2 04, s	$-\text{OCOCH}_3$	
20 7	$-\text{OCOCH}_3$	2 07, s	$-\text{OCOCH}_3$	
21 0	$-\text{OCOCH}_3$	2 16, s	$-\text{OCOCH}_3$	
<i>Methylene</i>				
22 6	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$	1 25 br s	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$	0 88, 1 59, 2 04
25 7	C-3'	1 59, m	$\text{H}_2\text{-3}'$	1 25, 2 19
29 3	$(\text{CH}_2)_y$	1 25, br s	$(\text{CH}_2)_y$	
29 7	$(\text{CH}_2)_y$	1 25, br s	$(\text{CH}_2)_y$	
31 9	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$	1 25, br s	$-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$	
32 3	C-6	2 04, m	$\text{H}_2\text{-6}$	1 25, 5 78
36 8	C-2'	2 19, t (7 2)	$\text{H}_2\text{-2}'$	1 59
61 3	C-6''	4 13, dd (11 3, 6 5),	$\text{H}_a\text{-6}''$	3 90, 4 10
		4 10, dd (11 3, 6 9)	$\text{H}_b\text{-6}''$	3 90, 4 13
67 0	C-1	3 95, dd (10 2, 3 6),	$\text{H}_a\text{-1}$	3 58 4 30
		3 58, dd (10 2, 4 0)	$\text{H}_b\text{-1}$	3 95, 4 30
<i>Methine</i>				
50 7	C-2	4 30 m	H-2	3 58, 3 95, 5 23, 5 75
67 1	C-4''	5 39, dd (3 9, 3 5)	H-4''	3 90, 5 00
69 1	C-2''	5 15, dd (10 7, 7 8)	H-2''	4 44, 5 00
70 9	C-5''	3 90, m	H-5''	4 10, 4 13, 5 39
71 0	C-3''	5 00, dd (10 5, 3 3)	H-3''	5 15, 5 39
73 9	C-3	5 23, dd (7 8, 2 5)	H-3	4 30, 5 37
101 1	C-1''	4 44, d (7 8)	H-1''	5 15
124 7	C-4	5 37, dd (15 1, 7 4)	H-4	5 23, 5 78
136 9	C-5	5 78, dt (14 9, 6 6)	H-5	2 04, 5 37
<i>Quaternary</i>			$5 \times -\text{OCOCH}_3$ and $-\text{CONH}-$	
169 4, 169 8, 169 9, 170 1 170 2 and 172 7				

[§]Values in parentheses indicate ^1H - ^1H coupling constant in Hertz (Hz)

further fractionated by preparative tlc to afford 1-*O*-acylglycerol (**2**) and 1-*O*-alkylglycerol (**4**). Treatment of the former with Ac_2O -pyridine yielded the diacetate **2A** and the same metabolite furnished the acetamide **2B** with acetone in presence of anhydrous copper sulphate. The diacetate **4A** was obtained from 1-*O*-alkylglycerol by the action of Ac_2O -pyridine. The ^1H NMR spectra and extensive homodecoupling experiments of all these compounds were in support of their structures adduced. The ^{13}C NMR spectra lent further confirmation to the structures **2** and **4** of the metabolites isolated.

Experimental

The crude residues were fractionated in each case by column chromatography (silica gel, 60–120 mesh, Tara Chemicals, Kolkata), preparative thin layer chromatography (silica gel G, E Merck) and final purification by chromatography on a short column of silica gel (100–200 mesh, E Merck). Spots were detected by staining with iodine vapour. All chromatography experiments were monitored by micro-tlc. Gas chromatography (GC) experiments were carried out on a Hewlett Packard M5890, Series II gas chromatograph fitted with a Hewlett Packard integrator M3394A.

The UV spectra were recorded in spectral alcohol (ethanol) on a Hitachi U2000 spectrophotometer and IR spectra were examined in KBr disc on a Perkin Elmer-782 spectrophotometer. NMR (^1H , ^{13}C , ^1H - ^1H COSY and ^{13}C - ^1H XHCORR) experiments were recorded on a Bruker AM 300L supercon spectrometer equipped with ASPECT 3000 computer fitted with an array processor using programme version DISR87.1 or DISR94.1 in CDCl_3 , unless otherwise stated, as solvent at 300.13 MHz for proton and at 75.47 MHz for carbon. Multiplicity of the carbon signals was determined from DEPT-135 experiments. The chemical shift values are in δ (ppm) downfield from TMS. Deuterio-solvent signal served as an internal standard in carbon spectral measurements; $\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta (\text{CDCl}_3) + 77.0$ ppm. Standard procedures were used for two-dimensional NMR experiments. Optical rotations were measured in a Perkin Elmer M241 electronic polarimeter at 25°.

Animal material : The marine organism (a sea mouse) *Chloeia parva* (Phyllum : **Annelida**, Class : **Polychaeta**, Family : **Amphinomidae**) was collected from the eastern coast of Bay of Bengal near Digha (latitude 21°37'N, longitude 87°31'30"E, which is about 180 km west of Kolkata), West Bengal and stored in a freezer until extraction.

Extraction and isolation : The raw organism (3 kg) frozen in liquid N_2 was crushed and extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (2 × 4L) and then with CH_2Cl_2 -MeOH (1 : 1) (2 × 4L). Solvents were removed under reduced pressure to afford the respective extracts (~4 and 2 g, respectively).

The CH_2Cl_2 and CH_2Cl_2 -MeOH (1 : 1) extracts of the organism were subjected separately to column chromatography over silica gel (60–120 mesh, 120 g) using solvents of increasing polarity. The eluates of each silica chromatogram were tested by running micro-tlc, fractions having identical spots were mixed up and the different fractions were purified further by preparative tlc over silica gel G using solvents of increasing polarity. The less polar eluates of the chromatograms afforded fatty acid methyl esters (FAME), cholesterol while the relatively polar CHCl_3 -MeOH (95 : 5) eluates yielded ceramide and CHCl_3 -MeOH (90 : 10) eluates gave 1-*O*-alkylglycerol and 1-*O*-acylglycerol. Again, the relatively more polar CHCl_3 -MeOH (85 : 15) eluates of the silica chromatogram of CH_2Cl_2 -MeOH (1 : 1) extract afforded galactocerebroside.

Galactocerebroside (1) : Colourless semi-solid mass (80 mg), R_f 0.3 in CHCl_3 -MeOH (90 : 10), $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} -1.4^\circ$ (*c* 0.96, MeOH); IR ν_{max} 3600–3100, 2920, 2855, 1640, 1620, 1540, 1465, 1455, 1370, 1070, 1035 and 900 cm^{-1} ; δ_{C} 13.6 (2 × CH_3), 22.4 (2 × $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 25.7 (C-3'), 29.1 (C-

7), 29.5 (*x* CH_2), 31.7 (2 × $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 32.3 (C-6), 36.4 (C-2'), 53.4 (C-2), 61.6 (C-6''), 68.7 (C-1), 69.0 (C-4''), 71.2 (C-2''), 72.2 (C-5''), 73.4 (C-3''), 74.8 (C-3), 103.6 (C-1''), 128.9 (C-4), 134.1 (C-5) and 174.3 (C-1').

1-*O*-Acylglycerol (2) : Colourless semi-solid mass (42 mg), R_f 0.3 in CHCl_3 -MeOH (95 : 5); IR ν_{max} 3500–3200, 2910, 2840, 1730, 1465, 1380, 1215, 1180 and 1040 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 5.35 (0.4H, m, olefinic H), 4.18 (1H, dd, *J* 11.6 and 4.6 Hz, H_a -1), 4.14 (1H, dd, *J* 11.7 and 6.0 Hz, H_b -1), 3.92 (1H, m, H-2), 3.69 (1H, dd, *J* 11.5 and 3.7 Hz, H_a -3), 3.59 (1H, dd, *J* 11.5 and 6.0 Hz, H_b -3), 2.31 (2H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, $-\text{COCH}_2\text{CH}_2-$), 2.01 (0.8H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CHCH}_2-$), 1.60 (2H, m, $-\text{COCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$), 1.25 [several, br.s, $-(\text{CH}_2)_x-$] and 0.87 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$); δ_{C} 13.8 (CH_3), 22.6 (CH_2CH_3), 25.0 (COCH_2CH_2), 29.7 ($(\text{CH}_2)_x$), 31.9 ($\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$ and $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}=\text{CHCH}_2$), 34.3 (COCH_2), 63.7 (C-3), 65.4 (C-1), 70.6 (C-2), 129.8 and 130.1 (~0.2C each, olefinic carbons) and 174.0 (CO). Methanolysis of the 1-*O*-acylglycerol fraction by boiling in methanol-sulfuric acid and subsequent extraction of the diluted reaction mixture with ether afforded a FAME which was resolved over a glass column (1.8 mm × 2 mm) of 10% DEGS in liquid phase supported on 80–100 mesh chromosorb W (HP) isothermally at 196° employing inlet temperature at 250°, FID detector at 250° and nitrogen flow rate 30 ml per min. FAME fraction composed of methyl esters of hexadecanoic acid (palmitic acid, 31.7%), octadecanoic acid (stearic acid, 28.5%), eicosanoic acid (arachidic acid, eicosoic acid, 7.1%), docosanoic acid (docosoic acid, 2.5%), tetracosanoic acid (3.0%), pentacosanoic acid (5.4%) as well as the unsaturated fatty acid 18 : 1ω9-octadecenoic acid (oleic acid, 17.4%) along with traces of other saturated and unsaturated fatty acids (< 2.0% each).

Ceramide [2*S*,3*R*]-*N*-acyl-2-aminosphinga-4,8-diene-1,3-diol^{31,32} (3) : Colourless amorphous mass (28 mg), $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} -4.1^\circ$ (*c* 0.29, CHCl_3); R_f 0.5 in CHCl_3 -MeOH (95 : 5); IR ν_{max} 3500–3100, 2955, 2920, 2850, 1645, 1625, 1550, 1465, 1375, 1055 and 970 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} 6.32 (1H, d, *J* 6.2 Hz, NH), 5.75 (1H, dt, *J* 15.3 and 5.8 Hz, H-5), 5.55 (1H, dd, *J* 15.3 and 5.7 Hz, H-4), 5.42 (1H, dt, *J* 15.2 and 5.9 Hz, H-9), 5.38 (1H, dt, *J* 15.2 and 5.9 Hz, H-8), 4.30 (1H, m, H-3), 3.94 (1H, m, H-2), 3.92 (1H, dd, *J* 9.6 and 3.4 Hz, H_a -1), 3.70 (1H, br.d, *J* 9.7 Hz, H_b -1), 2.23 (2H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz, H_2 -2'), 2.10 (4H, m, H_2 -6 and H_2 -7), 1.96 (2H, m, H_2 -10), 1.63 (2H, m, H_2 -3'), 1.25 (huge, br.s, *x* CH_2) and 0.88 (6H, t, *J* 6.2 Hz, 2 × $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$); δ_{C} 14.0 (2 × CH_3), 22.6 (2 × $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 25.9 (C-3'), 29.5, 29.6 and 29.7 (*x* CH_2), 31.9 (2 × $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 32.1 (C-7), 32.3 (C-6), 32.5 (C-10), 36.8 (C-2'), 54.8 (C-2), 62.4 (C-1),

74.4 (C-3), 129.0 (C-9), 129.3 (C-4), 131.3 (C-8), 133.4 (C-5) and 173.9 (C-1'). Methanolysis of ceramide fraction by boiling in MeOH-H₂SO₄ and subsequent extraction of the diluted reaction mixture with ether afforded a FAME fraction composed of hexadecanoic acid (palmitic acid, 47.5%), octadecanoic acid (stearic acid, 30.3%), eicosanoic acid (arachidic acid, eicosoic acid, 2.6%), docosanoic acid (docosoic acid, 4.2%), tetracosanoic acid (3.9%) as well as the unsaturated fatty acid 23 : 1-tricosenoic acid (8.2%) along with traces of other saturated and unsaturated fatty acids (< 2.0% each).

1-O-Alkylglycerol (4) : Colourless amorphous mass (60 mg); *R_f* 0.4 in CHCl₃-MeOH (95 : 5); IR ν_{\max} 3500–3200, 2910, 2840, 1460, 1380, 1180 and 1040 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 5.40 (0.2H, m, olefinic H), 3.85 (m, H-2), 3.72 (1H, dd, *J* 11.3 and 3.8 Hz, H_a-3), 3.64 (1H, dd, *J* 11.4 and 5.2 Hz, H_b-3), 3.53 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0 and 3.5 Hz, H_a-1), 3.50 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0 and 3.2 Hz, H_b-1), 3.46 (2H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz, H₂-1'), 2.01 (0.4H, m), 1.59 (m, H₂-2'), 1.25 (huge, br.s, *x* CH₂) and 0.85 (3H, t, *J* 6.7 Hz, -CH₂CH₃); δ_{C} 14.0 (CH₃), 22.6 (-CH₂CH₂CH₃), 26.1 (C-3'), 29.5 and 29.7 (*x* CH₂), 31.9 (CH₂CH₂CH₃), 64.2 (C-3), 70.5 (C-1), 71.8 (C-1') and 72.5 (C-2). The material 4 was converted to ditrimethylsilylether and resolved over a glass column (1.8 m × 2 mm) of 3% OV 17 in liquid phase supported on 80–100 mesh chromosorb W (HP) in gradient fashion (180–330°) with increase of temperature at the rate of 10° per minute, employing inlet temperature 350°, detector at 380° and flow rate of N₂ at 30 ml per min, whereby the presence of 1-*O*-dodecylglycerol (3.0%), 1-*O*-tetradecylglycerol (6.2%), 1-*O*-hexadecylglycerol (40.9), 1-*O*-heptadecylglycerol (6.0), 1-*O*-octadecylglycerol (27.2), 1-*O*-nonadecylglycerol (2.6), 1-*O*-dodec-3-enylglycerol (5.6%), 1-*O*-pentadec-6-enylglycerol (2.1) as major components along with some minor ones (< 2.0% each) were noted.

Cholesterol (5) : White crystalline solid (20 mg), m.p. 147° (CHCl₃-petrol), *R_f* 0.5 in CHCl₃-MeOH (98 : 2); [α]_D +39° (c 0.32, CHCl₃); δ_{H} 5.33 (1H, br.d, *J* 4.6 Hz, H-6), 3.52 (1H, m, H-3), 1.03 (6H, s, H₃-18 and H₃-19), 0.97 (3H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, H₃-27), 0.84 (3H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz, H₃-26) and 0.68 (3H, d, *J* 6.5 Hz, H₃-21); δ_{C} 11.7 (C-18), 18.7 (C-21), 19.5 (C-19), 21.0 (C-11), 22.6 (C-26), 22.7 (C-27), 23.8 (C-23), 24.4 (C-15), 28.1 (C-16), 28.2 (C-25), 31.6 (C-2), 31.9 (C-7, C-8), 35.8 (C-20), 36.2 (C-22), 36.4 (C-10), 37.2 (C-1), 39.4 (C-24), 39.7 (C-12), 42.2 (C-4, C-13), 50.5 (C-9), 56.1 (C-17), 56.8 (C-14), 71.8 (C-3), 121.5 (C-6) and 140.5 (C-5).

Fatty acid methyl esters (6 and 6A) : Colourless semi-solid mass (50 mg), *R_f* 0.75 in petrol-CHCl₃ (20 : 80); IR ν_{\max} 2910, 2840, 1730, 1465, 1380, 1225, 1180 and 1040 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} 5.35 (0.45H, m, olefinic protons), 3.66 (3H, s), 2.80 (0.1H, m, diallylic methylene protons), 2.30 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, COCH₂CH₂), 2.01 (0.8H, CH₂CH=CHCH₂), 1.59 (2H, m, COCH₂CH₂CH₂), 1.25 (huge, br.s, *x* CH₂) and 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz, CH₃); δ_{C} 14.0 (CH₃), 22.6 (CH₂CH₃), 25.0 (CH₂CH₂COOCH₃), 29.5 and 29.7 (*x* CH₂), 32.0 (CH₂CH₂CH₃ and CH₂CH=CHCH₂), 34.4 (CH₂COOCH₃), 49.5 (OCH₃) and 173.9 (CO). Gas chromatographic analysis established the material being consisted mainly of the saturated fatty acids (6) : hexadecanoic acid (palmitic acid, 25.0%), octadecanoic acid (stearic acid, 16.2%), eicosanoic acid (arachidic acid, 2.0%) as well as the following unsaturated fatty acids (6A) viz., 16 : 1 ω 9-hexadecenoic acid (28.5%), 18 : 1 ω 9-octadecenoic acid (oleic acid, 16.5%), 18 : 3 ω 3-octadecatrienoic acid (3.4%), 20 : 4 ω 6-eicosatetraenoic acid (3.0%) and 22 : 4 ω 6-docosatetraenoic acid (2.5%) along with traces of other saturated and unsaturated fatty acids (< 2.0% each).

Acetylation of galactocerebrosides 1 : Galactocerebroside 1 (25 mg) dissolved in pyridine (1 ml) was mixed with distilled Ac₂O (1 ml), warmed on water bath for brief period and kept at room temperature for 24 hours. Dilution of the reaction mixture with cold H₂O (50 ml) and subsequent acidification with aqueous HCl (1*N*; 20 ml) was followed by extraction with CHCl₃ (3 × 25 ml). The material obtained from organic layer was purified by column chromatography to yield an amorphous pentaacetate 7 (20 mg); *R_f* 0.5 in CHCl₃; IR ν_{\max} 3400–3300, 2955, 2920, 2845, 1750, 1680, 1505, 1465, 1370, 1240, 1170, 1070 and 1045 cm⁻¹.

FAME and Alc-OTMS from galactocerebroside 1 : The galactocerebroside fraction (8 mg) was refluxed with dry MeOH (2 ml) and conc. H₂SO₄ (2 drops) for half an hour. Then the reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and extracted with CHCl₃ (3 × 10 ml). Usual work-up of the organic layer followed by solvent removal afforded FAME fraction that was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (100–200 mesh). Finally the purified FAME (3 mg) so produced was gas chromatographed over 10% DEGS column and found to be consisted of methyl esters of 14 : 0 (4.4%), 16 : 0 (28.0), 18 : 0 (16.8), 16 : 1 ω 9 (9.2), 18 : 1 ω 9 (13.6), 18 : 2 ω 6 (2.0), 18 : 3 ω 3 (6.3) and 22 : 2 ω 6 (5.3) fatty acids.

The aqueous phase was treated with a bit of NaNO₂ and stirred for half an hour, then refluxed with NaIO₄

(5 mg) for an hour under N₂ atmosphere. The reaction mixture was cooled, extracted with CHCl₃ (3 × 10 ml). Usual work-up and removal of solvent afforded a material which was as such dissolved in MeOH (1 ml) and stirred with KBH₄ (~5 mg) in the cold on a magnetic stirrer for an hour, diluted with water (25 ml) and extracted with CHCl₃ (3 × 10 ml). Usual work-up of CHCl₃ layer and removal of solvent yielded fatty alcohol (3 mg) as a colourless semi-solid mass, R_f 0.5 in CHCl₃-MeOH (99 : 1) after purification by column chromatography (silica gel, 100–200 mesh). The fatty alcohol thus produced was dissolved in 50 μl of dry pyridine to which 45 μl of hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS) and 30 μl of trimethylchlorosilane were added. The vial was vigorously shaken for 30 second and the reaction was allowed to complete at 80° for 20 minutes and the content was directly injected into the column (3% OV 17). GLC analysis of the product allowed determination of the carbon chain length (as C₁₈) of the basic sphingosine unit.

1-O-Acylglycerol diacetate : 1-*O*-Acylglycerol (**2**) (10 mg) in pyridine (0.5 ml) was treated with distilled Ac₂O (0.5 ml) and kept as such at room temperature overnight. Work-up of the reaction mixture and purification as in the preparation of 1-*O*-alkylglycerol diacetate yielded the diacetate **2A** as a colourless amorphous mass (10 mg), R_f 0.6 (CHCl₃); IR ν_{max} 2910, 2840, 1730, 1470, 1385, 1215, 1175 and 1040 cm⁻¹; δ_H 5.34 (0.4H, m), 5.25 (1H, m, H-2), 4.32 (1H, dd, *J* 11.9 and 4.3 Hz, H_a-3), 4.27 (1H, dd, *J* 11.9 and 4.2 Hz, H_b-3), 4.17 (1H, dd, *J* 12.0 and 5.8 Hz, H_a-2), 4.13 (1H, dd, *J* 12.0 and 5.9 Hz, H_b-2), 2.32 (2H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, H₂-2'), 2.08 (3H, s), 2.07 (3H, s), 2.02 (0.8H, m), 1.60 (2H, m), 1.25 (several, br. s) and 0.87 (3H, t, *J* 6.3 Hz).

1-O-Acylglycerol acetamide : 1-*O*-Acylglycerol (**2**) (10 mg) was treated with dry acetone (5 ml) and anhydrous CuSO₄ (10 mg) and kept at room temperature overnight. The organic layer was directly spotted on to preparative tlc plate and developed with CHCl₃. Acetamide **2B** was obtained as a glassy mass (8 mg), R_f 0.7 (CHCl₃); δ_H 5.34 (0.4H, m), 4.30 (1H, m, H-2), 4.17 (1H, dd, *J* 11.5 and 4.7 Hz, H_a-1), 4.08 (1H, dd, *J* 11.6 and 6.2 Hz, H_b-1), 4.07 (1H, dd, *J* 8.2 and 6.4 Hz, H_a-3), 3.72 (1H, dd, *J* 8.4 and 6.2 Hz, H_b-3), 2.34 (2H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz, H₂-2'), 2.00 (0.8H, m), 1.61 (2H, m), 1.43 (3H, s), 1.42 (3H, s), 1.25 (several, br. s) and 0.89 (3H, t, *J* 6.3 Hz).

1-O-Alkylglycerol diacetate : 1-*O*-Alkylglycerol (**4**) (5 mg) in pyridine (0.5 ml) was mixed with Ac₂O (0.5 ml) and kept as such at room temperature overnight. The mixture was acidified with aqueous HCl (1*N*; 10 ml) and extracted

with CHCl₃ (3 × 20 ml). Usual work-up of CHCl₃ layer and solvent evaporation yielded a semi-solid mass which was purified by column chromatography yielding the diacetate **4A** as an amorphous mass (4 mg), R_f 0.4 in CHCl₃-MeOH (98 : 2); ¹H NMR δ 5.18 (1H, m), 4.33 (1H, dd, *J* 12.0 and 3.6 Hz), 4.16 (1H, dd, *J* 11.9 and 6.4 Hz), 3.54 (2H, d, *J* 5.2 Hz), 3.43 (2H, m), 2.08 (3H, s), 2.06 (3H, s), 1.25 (br. s) and 0.85 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz).

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